

Ascending the Interactive Multimedia Culture: The Lived Experiences of Aspiring Social Media Influencer

Efren L. Burgos, MAT^{1,2,3} Von Giese, Gwyneth Ghaile S. ^{1,2,3} Blanco, Byron Vince^{1,2,3}
Chavez, Mark Kevin M. ^{1,2,3} Cornejo, Justin Arnel P. ^{1,2,3} Encarnacion, Racel Gwen S. ^{1,2,3}
Hipolito, Alliah TJ S. ^{1,2,3} Marabur, Abdul-Raiz H. ^{1,2,3} Pacia, Abram Vinzell L. ^{1,2,3}
Roque, Liam John E. ^{1,2,3} Tuquib, Gem Danielle V. ^{1,2,3}

¹Philippine School Doha, Doha, Qatar

²Research Development, Accreditation and Publication Office, PSD, Doha, Qatar

³Research Capstone Project, PSD, Doha, Qatar

Abstract:-

Background: Over the past years, social media has become widely used by every individual. It has brought new opportunities as it grows every day. This study discusses Filipino and foreign aspiring social media influencers' lived experiences, who create content for the viewing public. **Methods:** This research followed a phenomenological research design in understanding the lived experiences of aspiring social media influencers relative to the central question: "What are the common strategies that aspiring social media influencers utilize to thrive in the multimedia world?" The data were gathered through thirty semi-structured interviews and were analyzed using an inductive approach to develop themes. **Findings:** The study reveals that every aspiring individual with diverse background shares common difficulties such as getting negative feedbacks and lack of inspiration for content, but they overcome them through their audience and self. Furthermore, this study shows how aspiring social media influencers have frequent trials being an influencer, how they build a relationship with their audience and the contrast between on and off cam. **Conclusion:** The aspiring social media influencers showcased their capability in adjusting and conquering the social media industry to maintain their position and further establish what they already have. It covers the complex unforeseen lives of aspiring social media influencers; they show how resilient they can be despite how harsh their work and ambition are. **Recommendation:** The researchers suggest that the range of participants be increased, interview influencers globally to encounter different types of content creators, and extend the number of following of aspiring social media influencers to further investigate the experiences tackled by aspiring social media influencers.

Keywords:- Digital World, Internet, Viral, Motivators, Network.

I. INTRODUCTION

Social media has become prevalent nowadays. It is a gateway of information and an opportunity between and among people of different races, cultures, and beliefs. It is a universal phenomenon that has bound people together. Social media refers to websites and applications that are designed to

allow people to share content quickly, efficiently, and in real-time Matthew Hudson (2020). Connecting and building a relationship with the audience are essential aspects of social media. Although there is no commonly accepted definition of what social media is both theoretically and functionally, it can be associated with the following categories according to Caleb Carr and Rebecca Hayes (2015); public relations, information technology, and popular press.

The powerful reach of social platforms has become a good avenue for propaganda. As such, many people are using media platforms to raise awareness, influence others, and sell products. Today, using it has become a daily and mandatory activity. The public representatives are the influencers; they build trust and connection through sharing their content with their audience. As said by Reto Felix, Philipp Rauschnabel, and Chris Hinsch (2016), Marketing in social media platforms is cross-functional, interdisciplinary, and is highly complex. Furthermore, instances where a company charges the customer more for goods and services identical with a competing supplier or services or demands anything at all for products that simply do not work.

Although social media posts may be a grave threat to people, it is, without a doubt, helpful. It can help young people develop their interests and find other people who introduce young people to new things and ideas and deepen appreciation of their existing interests. Social media and technology offer us greater convenience and connectivity: staying connected with family, friends, and other people worldwide via email, text, FaceTime, etc. It is quick access to information and research. A content creator is someone who has great influence over their followers on their social media sites. They have a notable reputation in their digital channel/s that allow them to influence the public over a certain topic of discussion. They make videos, take photos or simply create posts wherein the audience could see more of them, follow their suggestions, trust the creator, and generally sense their authenticity through the forum. With the trust that the creator made with their followers, they can start marketing their merchandise through social media. It is a great way to interact with your followers, giving them something that came from their favorite influencer. But, not all marketing can live up to their expectations.

During the COVID-19 outbreak, social media has become the saving vase for people to escape boredom, exchange information, express opinions, and seek assistance. People use the internet to lessen their anxiety about the virus; as stated by Araz Ramazan Ahmad and Hersh Rasool Murad (2020), during the lockdown, people are using social media platforms to gain information about COVID-19. Social media has played a key role in controlling anxiety about the pandemic outbreak. They use their influence to orient and emphasize matters according to their purpose. In other words, social media has given comfort and formed a distraction from the tension of the pandemic.

Taking all these points into consideration, this paper argues that aspiring social media influencers have various difficulties to conquer in entering the social media industry. Although aspiring social media influencers are people who have a built reputation for their knowledge and expertise on a specific topic, stated by Werner Geysler (2021), they create posts on the internet to captivate people and to entertain them. With wide categories as gaming, funny skits, animations, mukbang, music, etc. the content that these influencers do to keep and gain more following on social media.

The study's significance is to raise awareness to the new creators on how mass media exposure can be. The study can also be a way to introduce the situations and experiences of aspiring social media influencers that provides a new perspective to a profound understanding of what they see on and off the screen, including the different concepts and perceptions about being an aspiring social media influencer. The purpose of this study is to examine the roles, importance, and position of aspiring social media influencers in overall platforms. It also gives certain essence of understanding to the public on the everyday lives of the aspiring social media influencers who are heavily involved in their living.

This study analyzed and tackled the lived experiences of aspiring social media influencers. It provides a new perspective to the viewing public of the different sides of the internet community that only creators witness and experience. Social media has become a huge portion of society's lives and has evolved people to this day. Social platforms are very influential, both positively and negatively. "Being socially connected to others can ease stress, anxiety, and depression, boost self-worth, provide comfort and joy, prevent loneliness, and even add years to your life," as stated by Smith and Robinson, M.A. (2020). Communication, advertising oneself, quicker access to data, making a changer by raising awareness, and educating each other in various ways are some of the reasons why social media is a critical developer in today's society.

II. METHODS

A. Research Design

This qualitative research is inductive in nature. The researcher generally explores meanings and insights in a given situation (Strauss & Corbin, 2008). It uses a phenomenological approach whose main aim is to consider the participants' lived experiences. Phenomenology is a qualitative research technique that focuses on the mutual

features of a group's lived experiences. According to Tricia Chambers (2013), the approach's main aim is to arrive at a definition of the phenomenon's essence in question (Creswell, 2013). The participants' responses are the primary source of data that helps the researchers create a simulacrum. The researchers clustered and extracted commonalities from all the responses and used inductive reasoning from the participants' specific experiences that formed a thematic data analysis. With the help of the one-on-one interview that used a 30 questions guide, the participants could express their experiences as social media influencers. The researchers were able to understand and extract the lived experiences of the participants as influencers.

B. Research Locale and Sample

The research was conducted at Philippine School Doha (PSD) in Doha, Qatar, the leading basic learning institution in Qatar, as stated on its website (www.bnghghf.com). Since its inception in 1992, The Philippine School Doha, being a non-stock non-profit community school under the auspices of the Philippine Embassy and by order of Amiri Ordinance No. 7 of 1980, has been continually serving the growing population of Filipinos as far as the Philippine basic education is concerned governed by the Board of Trustees being the highest policy-making the body of the institution.

Fig. 1: Doha, State of Qatar; Mesaimer Area

The participants were all aspiring social media influencers who were selected with the following criteria set: Philippines/Qatar based, years of media influencing, and several following with a minimum of 500-1000 followers/subscribers from any social media platform. Some of them have permanent jobs, and one of their hobbies, apart from their job, is being an aspiring social influencer. They use various social media sites such as YouTube, Instagram, and others that can persuade other people to support their social media posts. Their creativity and being popular will be the key to getting more subscribers and followers. The job comes with interacting with people who comment on the posts. If aspiring social media influencers only write a small blog for cooking, the aspiring social media influencers still want to be able to answer questions from the audience. As a result, they earn extra revenue in what they post.

C. Data Collection and Ethical Consideration

The set of data gathered was through interviews via the “Zoom” platform, and interview guide questions containing central and sub-questions were validated by teachers to make sure the questions were appropriate for the topic and were utilized for obtaining data. A consent letter explaining the context of the study and contact information for inquiries were handed in beforehand. The consent letter was given to the interviewees also included the robofoto, which is utilized to obtain the respondent’s demographic profile as stated by Kristine Cielo Braganza et al. (2016). The interview guide was also used in following up on specific ideas or issues to explore specific experiences ensuring that the sensitivity of the subject being researched will float in participants’ consciousness (Fossey, 2001 as cited by Garcia & Acosta, 2016).

Following the research guidelines, the researcher asked their participants whether they would willfully have on/off cam, participants' availability set time/date, and permission to be recorded. The researchers had practiced confidentiality and assured the participant's security. In maintaining confidentiality, the participants' names were removed and referred to as P1, P2, etc. The personal information of the interviewees was blacked-out or excluded. Files containing the personal data of the interviewees are only shared among the researchers.

D. Data Analysis

The steps of thematic data analysis were followed, where the responses were examined and divided into their corresponding themes and sub-themes. To comprehend the data, the researchers; (1) listened to the participants' audio recordings to gain a better understanding of their knowledge on the subject; (2) transcribed the data that were collected through the audio-recording for emic transcription ; (3) doing emic-etic transcription by understanding the participants’ responses word by word ; (4) a cool-warm analysis through a dendrogram was applied to display the similarities of the responses were grouped into thinking units or the themes and sub-themes; (5) using the simulacrum to view the topic in a visual representation.

The second level of data analysis will use related literature to help strengthen the research study and further analyze the themes and sub-themes. The sub-themes are more specific topics, as they are grouped under the most relevant main theme (Thematic Knowledge Base, updated on November 29, 2021): (1) Influencers Personas’, (1.1) Platform Distinctiveness, (1.2) Ambition Orientedness, (1.3) Detail Meticulousness; (2) Online Interaction; (2.1) Content Sharing, (2.2) Online Connections, (2.3) Influencing Difficulties; (3) Holistic Health, (3.1) Healthy Living, (3.2) Balancing Routines, (3.3) Strengthening Relations.

III. FINDINGS

This phenomenological study depicts the lived experiences of aspiring Filipino and foreign social media influencers in the multimedia world. About the central question: "What are the common strategies that aspiring social media influencers utilize to thrive in the multimedia

world?" Moreover, this study has derived a specific question: “What are the common ways for aspiring social media influencers to stay emotionally and physically resilient?” The contrasting consequences of social media to aspiring individuals are inevitable.

Interconnected Components of Aspiring Social Media Influencer (Figure 2)

Fig. 2: shows the simulacrum focused on the three major themes:

Influencers’ personas, online interaction, and holistic health. The simulacrum was created through the participants' responses circularly to represent connectivity as a whole. The middle is shiny lenses that show the camera to symbolize the social media influencers' instrument. Behind the shiny lenses shows social media platforms used by the participants. The simulacrum consists of 3 primary colors with one sub color. The following colors represent particular meanings such as (1) Green: represents health and growth, (2) Light green: the uplifting feeling the influencers possess having a healthy body and mind. (2) Red: influencers' strong aura and persona whenever they show themselves online, bringing satisfaction and comfort to the people who watch them, (3) Light Red: represents the influencers' calm personality whenever they show themselves to the public, (4) Blue: the influencers' careful planning of their video and a color close to red serve as a warning that may damage their reputation, (5) Pastel Blue: encouragement, enthusiasm, creativity, and expression.

A. Influencers Personas

Influencers on social media have their style of content that they focus on with the help of their personality. To pursue their career as social media influencers, each potential influencer establishes an identity. There are different ways that influencers appear in their media; however, they all have their platforms, content, and personalities. Influencers attract their audience because of their common interests and personalities.

Platform distinctiveness looks at the types of social media platforms that influencer’s use and the way they

manage their social media. Each influencer has his way of pursuing his platform as a social media influencer. The influencers have their way of being distinct, and each has its platform. The participant talks about the associated platform and the type of content presented. Influencers have a choice to pick a platform they want to start on, and they also think up different types of content that they want to present. The platform and content matter due to the appropriateness of the media, the persona built, and the audience gathered.

“I’m a YouTuber, vlogger, and streamer. I’m a YouTuber and vlogger who’s simultaneously advocating print and audio-video media.” P5

“I am a photographer, I take pictures and show them to people.” P7

I am known as Reem Darwish and I’m an influencer on TikTok. P10

Ambition Orientedness focuses on the social media influencer’s goals. Rather than forcing themselves to accomplish what they don’t want to do, they concentrate on their goals by doing what they enjoy—following and pursuing their interests. They are inspired to keep going at their own pace because they value what they do. Several of them appreciate and are passionate about this profession. On the other hand, others see this as a motivation and inspiration they get from.

“My main drive is to educate and inform. Fake news is a thing and it should not just stop the person from informing the world either locally or in another country. It can affect real people, not just anyone or anything.” P3

“I always put in my mind my dreams and my future or in what situation I will have in the future so that I can help my family and also myself.” P4

“The fact my viewers watch and enjoy the content that I give is enough for my motivation to continue what I do, and I also really enjoy doing it.” P9

“I think about the feedback and the other photographers I idolize because they motivate me.” P7

“I usually continue what I am doing, and I put out more work out there and then you go from being a social media influencer, and then you go to the door, and then you go to be working with the more known people. So that is one thing that is keeping me going.” P10

Detail Meticulousness tackles social media influencer and their responsibility for providing the material they showcase, as well as how they create responsible decision-making in the process. They create their own set of rules to follow to make the best decisions possible while pursuing their career as social media influencers.

“I ask my followers on Instagram or sometimes on the actual YouTube comment section on what content they would want to see and that’s what I produce. So, I make sure that what I produce is something that they would watch and enjoy.” P1

“What I do care what’s popular things at the moment. On Instagram and YouTube, I follow popular vloggers and Instagram users and try the things they are doing. I do some trial and error to see what fits me.” P2

“I make sure my audience is satisfied with my posts by giving them originality and rare views they don’t see often.” P7

“If I make people want me or watch my content, then that would be staying true and realistic to myself as much as possible.” P9

“Everyone has their mentality. My mentality on social media is different from my mentality in real life. So, on social media, I would say my mentality is always to help people. I am a very active person and very open.” P10

B. Online Interactions

Online interactions are one of the main important factors to being an influencer. Another part is their personas as influencers which are tied to their Holistic health since what they show in front of the camera is completely different compared to what they show behind it.

In content sharing, there also comes the difficulty in influencing. The online connections lessen the effect of the previously mentioned subthemes. Content sharing in terms of online interaction is the way the influencers get their content around the multimedia world, and it is a part of the crucial areas of being an influencer, for it is what attracts the viewers and helps them become more recognized around the media. These, in turn, help the influencers grow, a way to rise in their specific platforms.

The participants shared common platforms and areas in terms of content sharing, such as Youtube, Tiktok, Instagram, Facebook, and Twitter. And the contents that the participants share mostly are about lifestyle, OOTD’s, challenges, video pranks, reviews of products, and education. On a side note, the participants also responded about their perspective on social awareness:

“This year, a lot of things have happened globally. I always engage myself like I try to help and empathize with others, depending on their background and culture. I also try to understand the social-ethical forms and behaviors of what I engage in.” P2

“I took perspective as a very important thing because not everyone thinks the same as me. Not everyone is as open and is as approachable as me. I consider perspectives as an important thing.” P3

“I try to understand the culture of the people and places, since here in Qatar, you can’t just document everything, like the people in hijabs, I have to be careful since they have a rule that they can’t have a picture taken.” P7

“By listening and observing, these are important when it comes to social awareness” P8

“When there are new things happening around the world, there’s a lot of awareness going on in social media, and I do my best to share it with the platform that I have even if it isn’t that big of an audience.” P9

Influencing difficulties in terms of online interactions is when the content does not reflect the interests of the audience, which could pose a threat to the influencers. Therefore, this leads to more obstacles and complications within the media world that the influencers themselves will face. A solid example would be their competition with other more well-known, more talked about influencers that have been in the media world longer than they have been.

Being a social influencer is not easy, though it may look easy when you see it in their videos. However, that is only just the tip of the iceberg. We haven’t seen yet what truly lies behind the curtains and the masks that they wear in accordance with what they’ve been through being one. Based on their experience, the participants themselves stated that:

“To produce new content all the time, it’s hard to be consistent. It’s part of you naturally. On the YouTube part, it is hard, it’s not like every day you have new ideas. That is my struggle now why I haven’t been posting on YouTube.” P1

“The struggles are somehow the judgement of a person. It somehow makes you self-conscious and it lowers your self-esteem” P2

“My struggle is when I have class in school, I can’t make my tasks and assignments on time because sometimes I prioritize my vlogs and I don’t eat regularly/properly because I stay up late at night editing my videos.” P4

“I’m not affected by dislikes on my vlogs but the ultimate struggle that I have is how to manage my schedule since I have classes to attend. So of course, you’ll be tired when the day ends. I told myself, despite being busy, I need to do my stuff regularly on YouTube.” P5

“Sometimes there are people who misjudge you. Especially when I post some stuff that is often misunderstood as showing off or bragging about myself. Not knowing that my only intention for them to try and experience the same things.” P6

“I struggle in thinking up themes since there are limitations here, so I’m forced to change plans.” P7

Online connections mean the connections between the influencer and their audience, the assistance they receive from friends and family, or from fellow influencers through recommendations in their videos which would be of great assistance to the influencers who need a boost in audience recognition.

The common feedbacks the influencers receive vary from each and every single one of them, but most of them are positive:

“So far, there’s no negativity. Their feedbacks are good. My friends and viewers are very supportive.” P2

“Most of them are positive and nice things or asks for some information on what filters I use or what apps I use. Sometimes rates and information about what services I provide on business terms.” P3

“They were thankful because they were able to refresh themselves. They were also thankful for the Arabic language that they could learn the basics. For the developmental news, I had the feeling that they also got lots of information from my write ups. So far, I have mostly received positive feedbacks.” P5

“It depends, people usually like more excited and looking forward for new content every day. That is one thing you have to present as an influencer.” P10

Despite looking good in front of the camera and having fun vlogging about their daily life, there is always a consequence to what they do. May it be positive or negative, one of which is that it is not always fun to vlog, especially when their viewers often talk bad about them, and because of it, sometimes it becomes tiring for them to continue making more vlogs and continue becoming a social media influencer. That is why they oftentimes try and do their best to keep up by means of coping with it along with their techniques in handling and managing the feedback they receive, as per what each of them mentioned:

“My family and friends. Whenever I receive bad comments, they are the ones I first consult. They motivate me and they give advices. Also, it’s already part of the industry so you just have to accept it.” P1

“The internet isn’t just a place for pictures but also for videos like personal opinion, forums, certified book, and advices. I cope by having me time. Blocking comments is great for mental health and stability.” P3

“Before I started YouTube, I already instilled in my mind that not everybody will like me. I told myself I could not satisfy everybody. Ignoring is the name of the game. They’re not my life.” P5

“Having a good support system and people surrounding you is really important because they can really lift you up and they can give you different perspectives, especially on how to improve or just be there for you at times when you’re down.” P9

Among the difficulties that social media influencers carry is the weight of how they are going to manage their audience, and with it comes the fact that some of them may give them a great and positive outlook, meaning that they have been a good influence on them and that they have been an impact in their lives in any way they could. However, it cannot always be like that; there are times when they have a negative impact in their lives and that it is either nothing much had changed for them or that they have drastically changed but not for the betterment of themselves which gives the social media influencers a “bad name” and negative

review in the multimedia world. In spite of that, according to the participants themselves, on how they manage their audiences, they replied that:

“Before, through Instagram only or other social media platforms like Facebook or the comment section on YouTube. Since my followers grew, we have a Facebook group where we engage with each other and also private chat rooms.” P1

“I always try to respond to them with optimism and try to engage with them as much as possible so they also understand how I see and appreciate them as an audience.” P2

“To maintain my healthy relationship with them I always reply to their comments or make a heart reaction to it and if they send messages to me I try to reply to them so that they won't think that I'm a snob person.” P4

“Before I started shooting or recording, I really conditioned my mind that everything is okay. I'm doing this because I love this and even if you're tired, I force myself to be okay in front of them, no negative vibes.” P5

“They share their experiences and journey with me. That is advantageous in being a social media influencer, it helps build friendships and connections with them.” P6

“You always have to communicate with your audience. You must always look for what they want. Look at the decisions you are making and what you are putting out there for your image. Communication, I would say is one big thing for the influencer.” P10

C. Holistic Health

The lifestyle of social media influencers claims to specialize in their wellness. Many good aspects of health and their influencers were discovered. The more advanced understandings of this concept were of a holistic, multifaceted, expanding condition in which all elements of health are interrelated and positively reinforcing. Social media influencers agree that health is more than just psychological well-being; but also involves more than just their psychological well-being and taking care of yourself in order to work successfully in front of and behind the camera. The study's data showed the following aspects of social media influencers' lifestyle, mental, and physical state.

Healthy living discusses the participants' concerns about maintaining their mental and physical well-being, as well as how they manage their wellness while working as social media influencers. This includes their techniques in engaging and encouraging their audience to adhere to their routines for maintaining physical and mental health. And how being an influencer benefit and harms their well-being. Most of them prioritize their physical and mental health in order to inspire others and have a great physique when they stand in front of cameras or an audience.

“It's hard to maintain your physical and mental health. When you are doing this career, our lives are based online and people's likes. It may not sound good but it's the truth. What I do when I sometimes receive bash, I just ignore them and

focus on my real followers and know how to continue and keep my channel on moving.” P1

“To give out good content on the positive side, you should have a stable mind. Being Physically healthy results in being productive in offering and giving informative content.” P6

“When I was a hundred percent doing vlogs on YouTube, I felt a little pressured because my viewers were asking for more content, and that can be emotionally and mentally draining, because aside from that, I have a lot of other responsibilities, but when I started to lay low, the pressure decreased and things became easier.” P9

“I take breaks. When I don't feel like posting, I don't force myself to post. I film my videos either morning or in the afternoon. I don't film late so that you don't lack energy when doing your content.” P1

“I would follow the intermittent fasting. 8 to 16 hours of eating period, 16 hours of fasting. But when work gets hectic, I give myself time to eat for energy. Not sacrificing myself to look presentable because the quality of my work is important and I wouldn't risk my health.” P3

“In the morning I'd usually have two pieces of eggs or tea, for lunch I try to limit my rice and in the evening some bread or fruits. But, sometimes I cannot control myself.” P5

Influencers motivate their audiences by sharing their diets and the foods they eat in order to encourage them to take care of themselves. They motivate others to live healthy and peaceful life when it comes to their health. A few participants discuss their self-consciousness and how they are unsatisfied with the content they produce; however, some do not yet have any emotional problems pertaining to their journey.

“I share the benefits of how good it is to exercise and encourage them. Also letting them know how drinking water can cleanse your body.” P2

“It's okay to inspire people but it's difficult to convince people to do what you are doing. To acquire the sense of willingness, self-determination and self-discipline for them to change for the better.” P5

“I just let them do what's best for them, because routines are different for each people, so if ever they would try out my routine, starting slowly and gradually would be good.” P9

“When I was starting it was emotionally hard because you will think that no one will support you. At first, you are scared of people's feedback. As time went by, it does not matter anymore. You lose care about it because you are already happy and so you just continue.” P1

“It is the people who are judging regarding the content I post. Especially when I have a blog website where my flaws in writing or displaying contents are being emphasized.” P6

"Being pressured a lot of times because the content is not enough for the viewers or it's just that I'm not putting my best content out there." P9

In addition, the influencers do feel uncomfortable and anxious, so they prepare themselves mentally and physically before facing the camera. They relax and find motivation by clearing their thoughts and warming up until they are satisfied:

"I don't post when I don't like it, so it's helpful because when people force you it does not help because it's forced. But in my case, it's healthy because I take breaks and I don't force myself." P1

"I'm in the proper state of mind, I could say that my mental state is healthy and well. There are times wherein you'd get dramatic but I think it's just a matter of managing stress and yourself." P5

"I don't think I am mentally stable right now, or healthy from social media, because of many situations. The only thing that's keeping me going is the positive side. And sometimes what you must do is go off social media and make time for yourself." P10

"Until now, I am not comfortable facing the camera. I try to conquer it and get used to it more often. The more you expose yourself in the camera the more you become confident with yourself." P2

"I already gave myself the benefit of the doubt that anything, like the viewers may not be satisfied with my content, and I know that as a social media influencer, that really comes along with it so preparing is what I do." P9

"I say to myself that it's okay, I feel it's okay, I feel good here, I think I did good content. So, I don't set my mind that hopefully many will like and love it; but I set my mind that I made myself happy, it made some people happy, and I think it for myself, not for others." P1

"As I said, you must always put your brave face when you're in front of the camera. That is one thing you need to do, mentally prepare yourself because you don't know if you are going to present a good thing or bad thing. So, you always must prepare yourself and always have a look at the bad side of things." P10

They all have different physical activities, and the majority are inclined to do cardio exercises. Some of the participants are focused on their exercise to lessen their stress levels since this helps them achieve their best physique that shows their determination. It makes them conscious and aware of their appearance as their followers' outlets continue to increase. They also uphold the desire to be a role model that could inspire and motivate their viewers to take care of their health as influencers:

"Running gives me energy and confidence, it gives me the feeling of fulfillment with work. It does keep me physically fit to continue and maintain having good health." P3

"A lot of physical activities but I focus on moving my body and being productive since it helps me become strong in the mind and reduces stress and anxiety." P8

"I try my best to maintain my physique, because somehow there are contents that I post that are related like clothes. Basically, it's my motivation on how to control what I eat. Though, it's not a strict diet and exercise." P1

"It makes me conscious on how I present myself. I try to balance myself, so that when I present myself online it's more properly organized" P2

"I keep being physically healthy as a social media influencer. We need to be healthy especially when the subscribers are getting bigger we really need to take care of ourselves in order to present ourselves well in front of them." P4

"I need to maintain physically healthy so that I could respond to my task in order to inspire and influence people." P5

In addition, Balancing Routines corresponds to how the social media influencers create a comfortable schedule that can accommodate their personal needs and time. They set their priorities and sustain a balance from their on and off screen life from being recreational and productive with their own set of hobbies and likes. Progress and exercise to stabilize their mental health and their physical fitness as their motivation to face the feedbacks from their viewers;

"It can maintain my peace of mind by limiting my use of social media within a day. So, I usually don't fully pour myself out on social media all the time so I can give my time to activities. So, that it won't be in my mind like all day." P2

"It helps me because I usually make and edit my vlogs alone. That's why it helps me to be able to think properly and to be good at thinking with regards to my contents." P4

"Maintaining peace of mind is relaxing especially when you are writing something there are benefits with it." P6

"When I receive some kind of negative comment, usually I tell myself to not pay much attention to it because it will not give me peace of mind, and the best way to respond to anything negative is to think if it's worth your time and energy." P9

Balancing routine discusses the techniques in managing themselves, organizing their schedules, setting their goals, and communicating about these effective routines to offer ideas and advice to their audience. The majority of participants' routines stated that their method of routine balancing is effective, while others are concerned about their physical well-being. Some individuals devise their own plans and conceptualize the factors that must be considered in order to effectively balance their diet. Respondents discuss how they manage and organize themselves, how they set goals, and how they communicate about their routines with others so that they can offer ideas and advice on how to make their routines more effective.

“It is effective because even if it’s not immediate, I could see the results, from time to time. And I am satisfied because it affects my work. I am more focused and energized towards my goals.” P3

“My routine is really effective. Aside from reading and studying I included my youtubing as part of my routine. Everything is planned and conceptualized so there was no issues.” P5

“Having a humble and having an intention that can influence the viewers. Having a goal to share what you can and keeping a grounded mind to not have an aim for motives like fame or power.” P6

The participants discussed how they manage, organize, set goals, and as well as how they communicate with others. Making the right decision at every step and managing their time in order to have a well-grounded self-management.

“I organize the things I do. I do not always prioritize the social media. I limit my time in social media so I can engage with the real world. I allot 1-2 hours for social media so that I can still manage myself.” P2

“Having a humble and having an intention that can influence the viewers. Having a goal to share what you can and keeping a grounded mind to not have an aim for motives like fame or power.” P6

“Communicate with your audience, look for what they want. Look at the decisions you are making and what you are putting out there for your image. Communication, I would say is one big thing for the influencer.” P10

Strengthening relations corresponds to their broadening of communication with audiences to establish connections through interactions and motivation that inspires them to strive with the support and care they receive. Some people communicate with their audience to engage and connect with them. Others are preparing and appeasing themselves. They build relationships with their audiences and followers by sharing their own life experiences, and some of them encourage their audiences to always stay positive in life and ignore the negativity.

“By showing their support. A lot of them message me personally. Asking if I’m doing fine or they miss me. You see that they are concerned about you, maybe that is also the reason why our engagement is good, especially my female followers, from time to time they message me and make sure I’m fine” P1

“By engaging with them. I ask them questions, what are their opinions on how they can help me in terms of common problems and they always try to respond.” P2

“They keep me physically and mentally fit in a way that I always put in my mind that I want them to see that I’m physically and mentally fit. I always prepare myself in front of the camera so that I will not be looking sick and unhealthy to them.” P4

Generally, the audience benefits influencers in many ways, especially when it comes to their mental health; their audience gives them positivity that enhances their confidence, which makes a huge difference to their health. This allows them to interact with their audience more, leading them to have a deeper connection. Besides that, the tips that will aid them in attaining wellness emphasizes staying positive, proper self-care, ignoring negative vibes, prioritizing the things that they want and make them happy, and setting realistic goals in life.

“It benefits me when I meet new people. Emotionally, it makes me happy to see people who positively engage with me.” P2

“It helps me because of the feedback I usually hear and see from my audience. It gives me strength to remain healthy and it gives me energy to do things in my everyday life.” P4

“I learned to ignore negative vibes and to stay away from negative people. Nonetheless I’m not frustrated with that because I know that humans do behave this way.” P5

“It helps me gain new friends and even new acquaintances just as it is, it also makes me burst my bubble and make me interact with more people.” P9

“When you’re doing these things, it’s hard to balance both physically and mentally. Like I’ve said, take breaks physically and mentally. Social media detox also helps because it affects how we feel, and the things we see online, like others are happy, or it’s so of this and that things. The focus is really take breaks and social media detox.” P1

“Do the things that make you happy and prioritize sleep. Without proper sleep your body is not going to function well even with preparation, and dealing with a lot of information and people, it is a main ingredient for you to be well. Physically have a good routine, keep yourself in checkups. Learn when to balance your time and schedule. Emotionally, if it does really affect you just turn those comments off.” P3

“First is surround yourself with good people, those who you know you’re sure and will lift you up, and second is simply being true to yourself, do what you want to do and if you don’t, then find yourself in that.” P9

“Always just focus on yourself. Do not forget yourself and you should always achieve for whatever is the best for you not for what others want to see from you.” P10

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Influencers Personas

In social media each influencer has their own persona that they use to their advantage in gaining followers. These advantages are what make them unique from other influencers, the participants explained that they have inspirations and mindset in getting into social media to be able to post content for their viewers and engage a rapport with the community that have benefits that will help them, potential influencers rise in their career.

It is defined that an influencer is someone who has power over their following. As the name suggests, an influencer is someone who has the power to impact the behavior of others. Social media influencers come from all walks of life and have tons of different target audiences. (Devlin, 2021). Some participants have stated that social media and the platform they are associated with is a hobby that they do for fun, it's also stated that enjoyment helps the participants continue being an influencer. In social media, an influencer presents himself/herself differently from others to make an impact to the viewers watching. These influencer audience personas can help influencers in crafting their social media posts and have more focused messages for their audience. (Jansen J, Salminen J, 2021)

The personas of the potential influencers are the audience's tastes and likings, a participant stated that the content posted in the platform is the manifested result from the opinions and comments of the audience. It is stated that it takes a lot of adjustment and motivation to continue in social media. Influencers have different personas that they were inspired by. The celebrity is an industrial formation and a point of production, generating a proprietary image-persona, which can be licensed as an aspirational endorser for other commodities. (Hearn A, Schoenhoff S. 2015.). Influencers create their own unique content for their followers. Social media personas are fictional representations of your ideal customers. Considering factors such as demographics, desires, personas paint a picture of the individuals you're trying to sell to. (Barnhart B, 2018) Internet personas develop as the influencer grows the audience and the consistency of the themes of the content. You can also define social media influencer as a person who works in a certain industry and collaborates with followers in, Social media influencer definition goes beyond the number of followers he can attract to your social media network or website. (Percherskyi M, 2021). Influencers also utilize the audience's opinions and suggestions, it helps them grow as a content creator and personality. Social media influencers develop a following by sharing quality content that inspires, entertains, informs, and connects them with their followers. (Asano E, 2021).

According to the Influencers, they manage their social media by themselves, and they are free to choose what their primary platform will be. The article shows that, despite inherent tensions and problematic ironies, self-branding persists through the rise of Social Media Influencers. (Khamis, 2016). Influencers' content is affected by several factors, including influencers' persona and the quality of their content. In addition, they may choose a variety of content types to present. Content and platform matter because the media, audience, and customer persona are appropriate. There is no hard and fast definition, but in essence, it is someone who has enough followers on social media, and typically YouTube, Instagram, or TikTok, that they can monetize it. (Kyte, 2021). The majority of the responses, according to the study, are across multiple platforms but have one major feature. According to Transcoso(2021) simply put a user persona stands for a representation of your target customer. When creating your user persona, some research is required to outline your customers' goals, pain points,

behavior, and demographic information. Their social media activity is focused on their hobby.

Those who do what they enjoy focus on their goals, following and pursuing their interests. Each of them has their own way of pursuing their own achievements and goals. When you align with an influencer, not only do they bring their audience, but they also bring their audience's network as well. Because of the loyalty of their audience, an influencer has the ability to drive traffic to your site, increase your social media exposure. (Patel, 2021). People are inspired by their own work and the inspiration the people around them give. Focus on an area you are truly passionate about, something you can create quality content for. In the long term you are going to struggle to maintain a high level of posting quality. (Vadlez L, 2019). Influencers incorporate their passion into the content or even is the base of their content. It is important for these influencers to also enjoy what they do as if it were an actual career. Influencers attempt to insert themselves into the subculture. (Wellman L, 2020). Influencers are also the audience, they put themselves in the position of being the audience and evaluate their own work. The thought process of the influencer is to be able to connect with the audience.

According to Esseveld, an influencer's followers are like gold and the more you can engage them, the more awareness and word-of-mouth recommendations you will generate. (Esseveld, 2021). Influencers can utilize the opinions of their audience and incorporate them into their work, it helps them adjust to the positive and grow as an influencer. Influencers come in many shapes and forms, so it is hard to pinpoint a common thread among all of them. At a basic level, influencers in the digital vernacular are individuals or sometimes small groups who exert a topical influence over a certain group of people through their online presence. In marketing, these people can be used in a variety of ways to promote a brand. (Dacko, 2021). In the current times, people are attracted to the trends which influencers take advantage of when thinking up of content to present which helps them promote and grow their platform. Focus on an area you are truly passionate about, something you can create quality content for. In the long term you are going to struggle to maintain a high level of posting quality (Vadlez L, 2019). The quality of the content matters to the audience, it is also important to establish an essence of what the primary content is.

B. Online Interactions

In social media each influencer has their own persona that they use to their advantage in gaining followers. These advantages are what make them unique from other influencers, the participants explained that they have inspirations and mindset in getting into social media to be able to post content for their viewers and engage a rapport with the community that have benefits that will help them, potential influencers rise in their career.

Some participants have stated that social media and the platform they are associated with is a hobby that they do for fun, it's also stated that enjoyment helps the participants continue being an influencer. In social media, an influencer presents himself/herself differently from others to make an

impact to the viewers watching. These influencer audience personas can help influencers in crafting their social media posts and have more focused messages for their audience. (Jansen J, Salminen J, 2021)

The personas of the potential influencers are the audience's tastes and likings, a participant stated that the content posted in the platform is the manifested result from the opinions and comments of the audience. It is stated that it takes a lot of adjustment and motivation to continue in social media. Influencers have different personas that they were inspired by. The celebrity is an industrial formation and a point of production, generating a proprietary image-persona, which can be licensed as an aspirational endorser for other commodities. (Hearn A, Schoenhoff S. 2015,). Influencers create their own unique content for their followers. Social media personas are fictional representations of your ideal customers. Considering factors such as demographics, desires, personas paint a picture of the individuals you're trying to sell to. (Barnhart B, 2018). Internet personas develop as the influencer grows the audience and the consistency of the themes of the content. You can also define social media influencer as a person who works in a certain industry and collaborate with followers in, Social media influencer definition goes beyond the number of followers he can attract to your social media network or website. (Percherskyi M, 2021). Influencers also utilize the audience's opinions and suggestions, it helps them grow as a content creator and personality. Social media influencers develop a following by sharing quality content that inspires, entertains, informs, and connects them with their followers. (Asano E, 2021).

As the world modernize and technology advance to be in the upper hand in the society, social media influencers are found in every corner in the realm of social media. They've done a lot of things such as helping nature restore what was lost and help us by giving new knowledge along with different types of discoveries along the way.

However, despite their contributions, they often experience difficulties when it comes to the content they create and share among the viewers in each and every platform they use. It may be on TikTok, Instagram, Facebook, Youtube, and etc. From that point, social media influencers had a lot of trouble getting the viewers they needed. As soon as their viewers kept on growing, they had to quickly come up with different ideas in order to maintain their viewer count. So, to quickly solve that issue, they themselves had to resort to asking help from other social media influencers, or if not them, may it be their friends or supporters. And that's where online connections come into play, they help the influencers gain more ideas to be used in making their next content in order to both help them grow as an influencer at the same time maintain their viewer count. It's not easy being a social media influencer, especially for the beginners who plan to create their own community filled with their patrons in order to become what society calls a social media influencer. To generate engagement and attract more followers, micro-influencers need to create high-quality content consistently. While this may sound easy on the surface, it's far from that. They need to come up with new content ideas that can engage their audiences, sometimes on a daily basis. At the

same time, these ideas need to be executed well, and for that, they need to invest a lot of time and effort as well. Hours may have gone into creating every single photo or video that you see on social media. (Shane Barker, 2019).

In this day and age of technology, social media, online interactions and connections are becoming more and more prominent, mostly when it comes to online selling and influencing. In that regard, it is shocking to see how much of it has affected us in many ways. Although there may be many difficulties, there are also many different ways and solutions to be able to decrease the main causes of their problems in terms of content sharing and the like. An example of which is writing down any words that comes to mind or words that comes out of their mouth, that way they'll be able to select from a variety of words to base their content on, another one is that they have to choose and select the audience that they want to have in order for them to be able to come up of an idea that will be used at the same time for their content creation if they ever want to grow and develop their group of patrons.

However, if they don't know which audience they would want to have, then their next best option would be their followers on any of their social media platform, ask them what kind of content they would want to see, so that they can get an idea and as well as be able to start their journey towards being a social media influencer for those who are just beginning. Some of these people have had ideas that many people latch onto and share with others about their newfound inspiration or person they admire. Eventually this person grows their following due to the content, ideas and information they share. This is a social media influencer. (Noonan, M., 2018).

Aside from the ways to gain more ideas for their content creation, online interaction is one of the keys to be able to get both ideas for content creation and at the same time gain viewers and/or assistance from other people who work in the same area as them, every online interaction has a social element to it, and every type of media is incorporating, competing with, or being replaced by UGC. (Luca M., 2015). For example, if he/she is a vlogger, and they need help with ideas for new content or maybe assistance for editing a vlog that you just made, they can ask another social media influencer who works in the same industry as them.

Interactions through the digital world have made its significance to us for it is a place where everything we want to know, discover, and explore can be found, online interactions made us quicker, convenient and efficient in terms of meeting someone, internet-based interaction have focused primarily on individual well-being, largely ignoring the potential benefits at more inclusive levels of analysis (community and society). We propose that one of the key benefits of online interaction has been overlooked by researchers: its potential to contribute to increased engagement with civic activities. (Pendry L.F. & Salvatore J., 2015).

By having online interactions, they can relax and be at ease knowing that they can get an infinite supply of ideas

flowing through their minds with either the help of their co-social media influencers or with the help of their patrons and followers. Moreover, it can also be challenging sometimes, since everything has pros and cons. Even other people as young as students can have difficulties in excelling through the online environment knowing they keep on having online interactions with either classmates or teachers as well. “Online interaction can be both rewarding and challenging. Students often have preferences for online or offline learning interactions, and they may select one learning environment over the other for varying reasons. (Fulton C. & McGuinness C., 2016).

Although online interactions have their pros and cons. Sometimes it also means having tones and voices throughout the social media platform. It can give the social media influencers a chance to be heard and give many different types of knowledge to their viewers in any way possible. This means that their viewers can both understand, learn, and discover a lot of things just by watching their favorite social media influencers. The more the social media influencers have a voice, the more they are recognized, and the more they have viewers who’ll learn from them. It may be the way they eat, the way they work, or the way they live. In short, their lifestyle can influence a bunch of their patrons and viewers. Interactions with a range of materials bring different tones and types of knowledge into one’s field of awareness. Particularly significant are online interactions in which a range of voices mix and merge. (Sukovic S., 2017).

These influencers stated their credibility and eminence in how they manage their physical and mental well-being in the face of realities, challenges and consequences. Even though there are negative aspects of pursuing a career as a social media influencer, they endeavor to manifest themselves into fulfilling their audience’s entertainment and self-satisfaction. According to the study, the majority of the responses are more motivated and encouraged to maintain their wellness because of their audience and how they are perceived. The influencers are more stimulated to continue their healthy practices as they are recognized as online role models. They bound their focus on positivity for it is not healthy for the mind and body. Having the control to divert their attention to the circumstances that matter and their time and energy have not withdrawn to dissipate.

In terms of strengthening relations, participants developed a strong bond with their audience by constantly interacting with them, sharing experiences and providing advice in life and career. As a result, influencers now have a better understanding of what their audience thinks and what their audience wants to know more about them.

In today’s media landscape, audiences are increasingly turning to online communities for media consumption and information exchange on interests such as health-related topics. Depending on the posts shared by influencers, consumers are impacted at four levels: increase in brand awareness, subject matter expertise, brand preference, and preference. (Chopra, A., Avhad, V., & Jaju, A.S., 2020). This necessitates a segmented approach in which interventions are related to online communities’ cultures and health-related

perceptions, and the dynamics of conversation and social influence in online networks. Influencers, the ones who influence, hold a firm grasp on people all over social media through their content, views, thoughts, and uniqueness that they have to offer. These influencers are known to impact people especially the younger generations. (Gupta, M., 2021). Strategies derived from the field of influencers offer opportunities to reach and engage with audiences in a personally relevant manner, including those who may disagree with the message. Social media influencers are first explored in the advertising field, particularly to create buzz in the younger markets and further expand social media coverage in businesses. (Lim et al., 2017). As a result, audiences take a different approach by leveraging influencers’ creative and cultural competencies, as well as aligning the methods with a media mapping protocol, to create influencer strategies related to the cultures and health-related perceptions of multiple online audience segments.

Social media influencers are more recognized in health and wellness topics. The popularity of influencers is continuous and does not have a limited window of influence. (Bhuvanewari, D., & Nisha, M.B., 2021). Audiences are reflecting on how influencers manage themselves and when it comes to choosing an influencer to follow, wellness has become an increasingly popular trend. Wellness has taken on a muddled meaning as each content maker, wellness properties contribute to a person’s holistic health. There are influencers who are more concerned with their health. Wellness encompasses a huge range of topics, including physical wellbeing, mental health, diet and nutrition, lifestyle, beauty, social habits, and etc. With the frantic pace of modern life, and the number of things competing for our attention at any one time, more people are looking for better ways to stay physically and mentally balanced (Joei Chan, 2019). Strategic influencer communication is a relatively new domain in communication management. Organizations and their agencies have to adapt existing or even develop new management routines for planning, organizing, and controlling their influencer activities (Nils Borchers and Nadja Enke, 2019).

As their followers continue to expand and get more acknowledged, the determination to maintain their drive to pursue being an internet influencer. Though they experience different sides being exposed to the world and their personal lives, they still find the procedure to sustain in strengthening their physical and mental health. “Some studies have indicated that social media use may be tied to negative mental health outcomes, including suicidality, loneliness and decreased empathy. (Berryman, Ferguson & Negy (2017). The ability to subsist themselves into valuing their health’s importance while focusing on their careers. Moreover, social awareness and global information dissemination strategies should take deliberate and meticulous preparation. Digital platforms offer an important means for improving the reach, scale and accessibility of community-based support for those dealing with mental health issues. They enable new forms of health participation. (McCosker A., 2018). Being pressured to manifest an image of being viewed as a role model to the public eye has taken a bearing on their mental health. Those who had the same self-concept with the influencers often

viewed them as role models in consumption. The increase of self-concept and brand image affected a consumer's purchase intention. (Hermanda, A., et. al, 2019). As for coping mechanisms, they coordinate their schedule that can accommodate their physical and mental well-being and put interest in communicating on the perspicacity of the people around them for encouragement and incentive. Thanks to their individual skills, specific knowledge or their personality, opinion leaders have a direct or indirect influence on the attitudes and decisions of consumers. In the contemporary globalized marketing using social media, this role is taken over by the influencers who affect consumers with their thoughts, attitudes and opinions and thus, significantly influence trends in demand for particular products. (Zak, S., &Hasprova, M., 2020). Public health organizations are increasingly turning to social media as a channel for health campaign dissemination, as these platforms can provide access to "hidden" or at-risk audiences such as populations of color and youth. (Kostygina G, Tran H, Binns S, et al., 2020). In concurrent times social media and the internet are high in demand and they use this opportunity and strive to devise content that can market themselves to attract new followers.

However, influencers also play an important role in social marketing strategies, such as promoting healthier diets, increased physical activity, less substance use and smoking, better quality of sleep, consumption consciousness on technology, health care seeking, increased adherence to medical treatment, and other health-related behavior. Until now, limited knowledge exists on how health interventions through social influencers can be implemented to effectively and efficiently promote important health behavior among their audiences (Frontiers, 2014).

The role of social influencers to change individual behavior around food and diet is growing each day. Influencers in Public Health have their role in influencing an individual's diet and food choices and the potential risks and benefits that it has for individuals (E.Byrne, J. Kearney and C. MacEvelly, 2017). Subsequently, we define strategic social media communication as the purposeful use of communication by organizations or social media influencers in which influencers are addressed to activities with strategic significance to organizational goals. We then situate these definitions within the broader framework of strategic communication by discussing related concepts and by describing the strategic action field that has emerged around strategic social media influencer communication (Nadja Enke& Nils Borchers, 2019). There are also opportunities to amplify tailored health communications in the target audiences' media realities not merely by focusing on sending messages, but also by stimulating (online) conversations and other forms of online audience engagement (Lutkenhaus, Jansz, & Bouman, 2019). Work-life balance is discussed for various decades and measured with different dimensions, this is high time to measure work-life balance in accordance with present lifestyle. Here comes the role of the internet which is twisted with every human being in day to day activities. The Internet without social media is unimaginable. Usage of social media results in both productive and unproductive behaviour. It is found that social media usage in professional

life has more impact on work-life balance which is caused due to preoccupation with social media in the workplace (Kumar A. and Priyadarshini, 2018).

Content Sharing is how the content of the influencers circulates the multimedia world. May it be through sharing by friends and or family, through recommendations or other ways presented online. Content sharing could either be helpful or a hindrance to aspiring influencers in establishing and reaching out to their communities. Improving content sharing on social media platforms helps firms enhance the efficacy of their marketing campaigns. The authors study the impact of network overlap—the overlap in network connections between two users—on content sharing in directed social media platforms. (Peng, J., Agarwal, A., Hosanagar, K., & Iyengar, R., 2018). According to the study, 49% of respondents share as it allows them to inform others of products they care about and potentially change opinions or encourage actions. ... 94% of respondents also said that they carefully consider how the information they share will be useful to the recipient. (Team, F., 2021). as with any marketing effort, you should be experimenting and optimizing with the frequency and timing of your content sharing. As you build a following, finding the right time to post on social media can make huge differences in the amount of traffic your content gets. (Media, M. D. S., 2019).

Online connections are the links between the influencers and their communities, influencers to other influencers, and influencers to their management as required as soon as they have gained recognition and have their mark on the multimedia world. These could also be helpful or a hindrance to aspiring influencers as they start off with a few connections (i.e. friends and families) which could provide them very little help. While none of us can expect to have a real, face-to-face connection with every one of our contacts, we should strive to translate at least some of those online relationships into the real world. One quick way to gauge how you're doing is by simply asking yourself how often you get in touch with your social media connections outside of the social media platform. (Hyder, S., 2017). Fortunately, it's possible to turn online connections into real-life ones. The problem is that most of us are taking the wrong approach to these relationships, says Ferrazzi, who is also CEO of Ferrazzi Greenlight, a research and consulting firm. We rely on serendipity to make things happen. Sometimes that works, but often it doesn't. (Vanderkam L., 2014). Search your social media connections one at a time and decide who you want to have as a customer. Most of your online connections are potential customers, so don't be afraid to start the offline connection. (Duran B., 2021).

Influencing difficulties are the hindrances and obstacles that the influencers face as they struggle to name themselves in the multimedia world. These may vary differently from each influencer as they put out different types of content online which the viewers might dislike, disapprove of, or fully ignore. The challenge is influencing others is learning how to influence others without sounding or looking artificial. I suppose the best approach is to try and if that doesn't work... try again. (Ouellette D., 2012). The current situation is creating many new threats that stimulate a fear response. If

your idea/solution can help remove some of these fears, either at the individual or organizational level, then it will be completely congruent with the current climate. These new challenges are likely to continue to change as the crisis continues, people find solutions to some problems and others arise. (Connors, D., & Drew, G., 2020). Since companies now have a harder time reaching out to consumers, social media influencers have been used as a solution to influence the purchase decisions of consumers and thereby drive purchases. However, while social media influencers are said to have an impact on the purchase decisions of consumers, less is actually known about the influence on all stages of the purchase decision process. As the purchase decision is not solely based on its own but rather follows from a series of steps, also called the purchase decision process, more research based on this area is of importance. (Gashi, L., 2017).

C. Holistic Health

In social media each influencer has their own persona that they use to their advantage in gaining followers. These advantages are what make them unique from other influencers, the participants explained that they have inspirations and mindset in getting into social media to be able to post content for their viewers and engage a rapport with the community that have benefits that will help them, potential influencers rise in their career.

Some participants have stated that social media and the platform they are associated with is a hobby that they do for fun, it's also stated that enjoyment helps the participants continue being an influencer. In social media, an influencer presents himself/herself differently from others to make an impact to the viewers watching. These influencer audience personas can help influencers in crafting their social media posts and have more focused messages for their audience. (Jansen J, Salminen J, 2021).

The personas of the potential influencers are the audience's tastes and likings, a participant stated that the content posted in the platform is the manifested result from the opinions and comments of the audience. It is stated that it takes a lot of adjustment and motivation to continue in social media. Influencers have different personas that they were inspired by. The celebrity is an industrial formation and a point of production, generating a proprietary image-persona, which can be licensed as an aspirational endorser for other commodities. (Hearn A, Schoenhoff S. 2015.). Influencers create their own unique content for their followers. Social media personas are fictional representations of your ideal customers. Considering factors such as demographics, desires, personas paint a picture of the individuals you're trying to sell to. (Barnhart B, 2018). Internet personas develop as the influencer grows the audience and the consistency of the themes of the content. You can also define social media influencer as a person who works in a certain industry and collaborates with followers in, Social media influencer definition goes beyond the number of followers he can attract to your social media network or website. (Percherskyi M, 2021). Influencers also utilize the audience's opinions and suggestions, it helps them grow as a content creator and personality. Social media influencers develop a following by

sharing quality content that inspires, entertains, informs, and connects them with their followers. (Asano E, 2021).

As the world modernizes and technology advances to be in the upper hand in society, social media influencers are found in every corner in the realm of social media. They've done a lot of things such as helping nature restore what was lost and help us by giving new knowledge along with different types of discoveries along the way.

However, despite their contributions, they often experience difficulties when it comes to the content they create and share among the viewers in each and every platform they use. It may be on TikTok, Instagram, Facebook, Youtube, and etc. From that point, social media influencers had a lot of trouble getting the viewers they needed. As soon as their viewers kept on growing, they had to quickly come up with different ideas in order to maintain their viewer count. So, to quickly solve that issue, they themselves had to resort to asking help from other social media influencers, or if not them, may it be their friends or supporters. And that's where online connections come into play, they help the influencers gain more ideas to be used in making their next content in order to both help them grow as an influencer at the same time maintain their viewer count. It's not easy being a social media influencer, especially for the beginners who plan to create their own community filled with their patrons in order to become what society calls a social media influencer. To generate engagement and attract more followers, micro-influencers need to create high-quality content consistently. While this may sound easy on the surface, it's far from that. They need to come up with new content ideas that can engage their audiences, sometimes on a daily basis. At the same time, these ideas need to be executed well, and for that, they need to invest a lot of time and effort as well. Hours may have gone into creating every single photo or video that you see on social media. (Shane Barker, 2019).

In this day and age of technology, social media, online interactions and connections are becoming more and more prominent, mostly when it comes to online selling and influencing. In that regard, it is shocking to see how much of it has affected us in many ways. Although there may be many difficulties, there are also many different ways and solutions to be able to decrease the main causes of their problems in terms of content sharing and the like. An example of which is writing down any words that comes to mind or words that comes out of their mouth, that way they'll be able to select from a variety of words to base their content on, another one is that they have to choose and select the audience that they want to have in order for them to be able to come up of an idea that will be used at the same time for their content creation if they ever want to grow and develop their group of patrons.

However, if they don't know which audience they would want to have, then their next best option would be their followers on any of their social media platform, ask them what kind of content they would want to see, so that they can get an idea and as well as be able to start their journey towards being a social media influencer for those who are just beginning. Some of these people have had ideas

that many people latch onto and share with others about their newfound inspiration or person they admire. Eventually this person grows their following due to the content, ideas and information they share. This is a social media influencer. (Noonan, M., 2018).

Aside from the ways to gain more ideas for their content creation, online interaction is one of the keys to be able to get both ideas for content creation and at the same time gain viewers and/or assistance from other people who work in the same area as them, every online interaction has a social element to it, and every type of media is incorporating, competing with, or being replaced by UGC. (Luca M., 2015). For example, if he/she is a vlogger, and they need help with ideas for new content or maybe assistance for editing a vlog that you just made, they can ask another social media influencer who works in the same industry as them.

Interactions through the digital world have made its significance to us for it is a place where everything we want to know, discover, and explore can be found, online interactions made us quicker, convenient and efficient in terms of meeting someone, internet-based interaction have focused primarily on individual well-being, largely ignoring the potential benefits at more inclusive levels of analysis (community and society). We propose that one of the key benefits of online interaction has been overlooked by researchers: its potential to contribute to increased engagement with civic activities. (Pendry L.F. & Salvatore J., 2015).

By having online interactions, they can relax and be at ease knowing that they can get an infinite supply of ideas flowing through their minds with either the help of their co-social media influencers or with the help of their patrons and followers. Moreover, it can also be challenging sometimes, since everything have pros and cons. Even other people as young as students can have difficulties in excelling through the online environment knowing they keep on having online interactions with either classmates or teachers as well. Online interaction can be both rewarding and challenging. Students often have preferences for online or offline learning interactions, and they may select one learning environment over the other for varying reasons. (Fulton C. & McGuinness C., 2016).

Although online interactions have their pros and cons. Sometimes it also means having tones and voices throughout the social media platform. It can give the social media influencers a chance to be heard and give many different types of knowledge to their viewers in any way possible. This means that their viewers can both understand, learn, and discover a lot of things just by watching their favorite social media influencers. The more the social media influencers have a voice, the more they are recognized, and the more they have viewers who'll learn from them. It may be the way they eat, the way they work, or the way they live. In short, their lifestyle can influence a bunch of their patrons and viewers, interactions with a range of materials bring different tones and types of knowledge into one's field of awareness. Particularly significant are online interactions in which a range of voices mix and merge. (Sukovic S., 2017).

These influencers stated their credibility and eminence in how they manage their physical and mental well-being in the face of realities, challenges and consequences. Even though there are negative aspects of pursuing a career as a social media influencer, they endeavor to manifest themselves into fulfilling their audience's entertainment and self-satisfaction. According to the study, the majority of the responses are more motivated and encouraged to maintain their wellness because of their audience and how they are perceived. The influencers are more stimulated to continue their healthy practices as they are recognized as online role models. They bound their focus on positivity for it is not healthy for the mind and body. Having the control to advert their attention to the circumstances that matter and their time and energy have not withdrawn to dissipate.

In terms of strengthening relations, participants developed a strong bond with their audience by constantly interacting with them, sharing experiences and providing advice in life and career. As a result, influencers now have a better understanding of what their audience thinks and what their audience wants to know more about them.

In today's media landscape, audiences are increasingly turning to online communities for media consumption and information exchange on interests such as health-related topics. Depending on the posts shared by influencers, consumers are impacted at four levels: increase in brand awareness, subject matter expertise, brand preference, and preference. (Chopra, A., Avhad, V., & Jaju, A.S., 2020). This necessitates a segmented approach in which interventions are related to online communities' cultures and health-related perceptions, and the dynamics of conversation and social influence in online networks. Influencers, the ones who influence, hold a firm grasp on people all over social media through their content, views, thoughts, and uniqueness that they have to offer. These influencers are known to impact people especially the younger generations. (Guptaa, M., 2021). Strategies derived from the field of influencers offer opportunities to reach and engage with audiences in a personally relevant manner, including those who may disagree with the message. Social media influencers are first explored in the advertising field, particularly to create buzz in the younger markets and further expand social media coverage in businesses. (Lim et al., 2017). As a result, audiences take a different approach by leveraging influencers' creative and cultural competencies, as well as aligning the methods with a media mapping protocol, to create influencer strategies related to the cultures and health-related perceptions of multiple online audience segments.

Social media influencers are more recognized in health and wellness topics. The popularity of influencers is continuous and does not have a limited window of influence. (Bhuvanewari, D., & Nisha, M.B., 2021). Audiences are reflecting on how influencers manage themselves and when it comes to choosing an influencer to follow, wellness has become an increasingly popular trend. Wellness has taken on a muddled meaning as each content maker, wellness properties contribute to a person's holistic health. There are influencers who are more concerned with

their health. Wellness encompasses a huge range of topics, including physical wellbeing, mental health, diet and nutrition, lifestyle, beauty, social habits, and etc. With the frantic pace of modern life, and the number of things competing for our attention at any one time, more people are looking for better ways to stay physically and mentally balanced (Joel Chan, 2019). Strategic influencer communication is a relatively new domain in communication management. Organizations and their agencies have to adapt existing or even develop new management routines for planning, organizing, and controlling their influencer activities (Nils Borchers and Nadja Enke, 2019).

As their followers continue to expand and get more acknowledged, the determination to maintain their drive to pursue being an internet influencer. Though they experience different sides being exposed to the world and their personal lives, they still find the procedure to sustain in strengthening their physical and mental health. Some studies have indicated that social media use may be tied to negative mental health outcomes, including suicidality, loneliness and decreased empathy. (Berryman, Ferguson & Negy (2017). The ability to subsist themselves into valuing their health's importance while focusing on their careers. Moreover, social awareness and global information dissemination strategies should take deliberate and meticulous preparation. Digital platforms offer an important means for improving the reach, scale and accessibility of community-based support for those dealing with mental health issues. They enable new forms of health participation. (McCosker A., 2018). Being pressured to manifest an image of being viewed as a role model to the public eye has taken a bearing on their mental health. Those who had the same self-concept with the influencers often viewed them as role models in consumption. The increase of self-concept and brand image affected a consumer's purchase intention. (Hermanda, A., et. al, 2019). As for coping mechanisms, they coordinate their schedule that can accommodate their physical and mental well-being and put interest in communicating on the perspicacity of the people around them for encouragement and incentive. Thanks to their individual skills, specific knowledge or their personality, opinion leaders have a direct or indirect influence on the attitudes and decisions of consumers. In the contemporary globalized marketing using social media, this role is taken over by the influencers who affect consumers with their thoughts, attitudes and opinions and thus, significantly influence trends in demand for particular products. (Zak, S., & Hasprova, M., 2020). Public health organizations are increasingly turning to social media as a channel for health campaign dissemination, as these platforms can provide access to "hidden" or at-risk audiences such as populations of color and youth. (Kostygina G, Tran H, Binns S, et al., 2020). In concurrent times social media and the internet are high in demand and they use this opportunity and strive to devise content that can market themselves to attract new followers.

However, influencers also play an important role in social marketing strategies, such as promoting healthier diets, increased physical activity, less substance use and smoking, better quality of sleep, consumption consciousness on technology, health care seeking, increased adherence to

medical treatment, and other health-related behavior. Until now, limited knowledge exists on how health interventions through social influencers can be implemented to effectively and efficiently promote important health behavior among their audiences (Frontiers, 2014).

The role of social influencers to change individual behavior around food and diet is growing each day. Influencers in Public Health have their role in influencing an individual's diet and food choices and the potential risks and benefits that it has for individuals (E. Byrne, J. Kearney and C. MacEvilly, 2017). Subsequently, we define strategic social media communication as the purposeful use of communication by organizations or social media influencers in which influencers are addressed to activities with strategic significance to organizational goals. We then situate these definitions within the broader framework of strategic communication by discussing related concepts and by describing the strategic action field that has emerged around strategic social media influencer communication (Nadja Enke & Nils Borchers, 2019). There are also opportunities to amplify tailored health communications in the target audiences' media realities not merely by focusing on sending messages, but also by stimulating (online) conversations and other forms of online audience engagement (Lutkenhaus, Jansz, & Bouman, 2019). Work-life balance is discussed for various decades and measured with different dimensions, this is high time to measure work-life balance in accordance with present lifestyle. Here comes the role of the internet which is twisted with every human being in day to day activities. The Internet without social media is unimaginable. Usage of social media results in both productive and unproductive behaviour. It is found that social media usage in professional life has more impact on work-life balance which is caused due to preoccupation with social media in the workplace (Kumar A. and Priyadarshini, 2018).

V. CONCLUSION

As based from the study's simulacrum, the researchers identified the diversity of the influencers on how they approach social media. The research shows collective difficulties and how these influencers cope with such obstacles or struggles. The study also shows the great bond between aspiring social media influencer and a follower including its significant effects of the activities done by creators that aid to the dissemination of necessary information online.

This study has created a framework that allows future research to take off from as it provides a new angle for the complex lives of these creators on and off-cam. Moreover, it attempts to raise awareness of the creators' involvement and exposure to mass media thus introducing certain instances and experiences that would provide a profound insight and understanding such as the different concepts and perceptions about being a social media influencer to the mass community as it presents a uniform understanding of the different statuses of the content creators. These online platforms that are considered home to influencers have a vast and notable power control over the general public. Whether its role is for people to escape boredom, exchange information, express

opinions, and seek assistance; social Media has become a portion of society's lives and has evolved the people online to this day as it can mold and affect us both positively or negatively.

As the public most frequently hear that the use of social media could effortlessly affect oneself, whether it be good or bad, the talks about the lived experience of social media influencers are seldom discussed. This study broadens and magnifies over the different sides of the internet community that only creators witness and experience.

Without the warmth that is felt around society, these influencers detect and perceives as if there is no use in terms of being a role model to the people online. As these content creators covers a substantial and pivotal role in our community as it simultaneously generates a toxic environment thus leading them to be cyberbullying-prone and in some instances these situations could greatly affect the influencer's health that no individuals get to experience other than influencers themselves.

The researchers recommend increasing the range of participants of influencers in social media, and interview creators globally with different types of contents, to possess a deeper understanding of influencers and their subject of ideas as well as the experience they go through. Another is to broaden the number of following of the social media influencer to further know their experiences since they have bigger audience. Lastly, the researcher recommends to tackle if the number of years of influencing matter. Having good communication and the love and support among family and friends can help boost the esteem of the influencers. It can add meaning to the purpose of being a public figure including going through any obstacles that may come along in their way. Another factor that that is caused by support of each person is the content that can help others to entertain, convince, educate, and inspire the audience to be a fellow content creator.

Since social media is evident throughout the 21st century, without these influencers competent in the digital world, there is no person to guide people through the internet, no leader nor direction to follow. Inside the digital world can be complex for the youth and the elderly, seeing the contents that they online could easily overwhelm a person, through the guidance of these creators would help them better understand and get used to the modern times.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Ahmad, A. R., & Murad, H. R. (2020, May 19). The impact of social media on panic during the COVID-19 pandemic in Iraqi Kurdistan: Online questionnaire study. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*. <https://www.jmir.org/2020/5/e19556/>
- [2.] Asano, (2021) What Constitutes an influencer? <https://mediakix.com/blog/influencer-definition-marketing/>
- [3.] Barker, S. (2019, August 20). 5 Challenges Most Micro-Influencers Deal With. Retrieved September 21, 2021, from <https://thenextscoop.com/challenges-micro-influencers-deal-with/>
- [4.] Berryman, C., Ferguson, C.J. & Negy, C. (2018). Social Media Use and Mental Health among Young Adults. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11126-017-9535-6>
- [5.] Bhuvanewari, D., & Nisha, M.B. (2021). IMPACT OF INFLUENCER MARKETING ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOR WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO ONLINE COURSES. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/IMPACT-OF-INFLUENCER-MARKETING-ON-CONSUMER-BEHAVIOR-Bhuvanewari-Nisha/dedffe12b520ab313ded6e7c632854364a85be49>
- [6.] Borchers, N. & Enke, N. (2019). Managing strategic influencer communication: A systematic overview on emerging planning, organization, and controlling routines <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0363811121000333>
- [7.] Byrne, E., Kearney, J. & MacEvilly, C. (2017). The Role of Influencer Marketing and Social Influencers in Public Health <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/proceedings-of-the-nutrition-society/article/role-of-influencer-marketing-and-social-influencers-in-public-health/94BF63FEFB6C94837808777921156BD1>
- [8.] Chambers, T. (2013, July 11). Phenomenological research | Qualitative research in corporate communication. Waiting for the redirect... <https://blogs.baruch.cuny.edu/com9640epstein/?p=543>
- [9.] Chopra, A., Avhad, V., & Jaju, A.S. (2020). Influencer Marketing: An Exploratory Study to Identify Antecedents of Consumer Behavior of Millennial. *Business Perspectives and Research*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Influencer-Marketing%3A-An-Exploratory-Study-to-of-of-Chopra-Avhad/814992fac7937ea2c486ea20e7f4a785c0a9625e>
- [10.] Connors, D., & Drew, G. (2020, April 21). Top 5 influence challenges our clients are facing (via Passle). Passle. Retrieved December 1, 2021, from <http://influence.appliedinfluencegroup.com/post/102g4nu/top-5-influence-challenges-our-clients-are-facing>. Hudson, M. (2020, June 23). What is social media: <https://www.thebalancesmb.com/what-is-social-media-2890301>
- [11.] Corbin, J., & Strauss, A. (2008). *Prelude to analysis - SAGE research methods*. SAGE Research Methods: Find resources to answer your research methods and statistics questions. <https://methods.sagepub.com/book/basics-of-qualitative-research/n3.xml>
- [12.] Dacko, (2021) How Do You Define an Influencer? The Answer Has Shifted <https://www.hyprbrands.com/blog/how-do-you-define-an-influencer>
- [13.] Devlin, (2021) The Hidden Dangers of Being an Influencer <https://www.makeuseof.com/dangers-of-being-influencer/>
- [14.] Duran, B. (2021, June 14). Turn your online connections into offline relationships and loyal customers in 3 simple steps! LinkedIn. Retrieved December 1, 2021, from <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/turn-your-online-connections-offline-relationships-loyal-duran>

- [15.] Enke, N. & Borchers N. (2019). Social media influencers in strategic communication: A conceptual framework for strategic social media influencer communication <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/1553118X.2019.1620234>
- [16.] Esseveld, (2021) Why goals matter to influencer marketing success <https://business.twitter.com/en/blog/why-goals-matter-to-influencer-marketing-success.html>
- [17.] Fulton, C., & McGuinness, C. (2021, July 21). Online interaction. Online Interaction - an overview | ScienceDirect Topics. Retrieved September 21, 2021, from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/social-sciences/online-interaction>
- [18.] Gashi, L. (2017, October 19). Social Media influencers - why we cannot ignore them: An exploratory study about how consumers perceive the influence of social media influencers during the different stages of the purchase decision process. DIVA. Retrieved December 1, 2021, from <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2%3A1149282&dsid=8627>
- [19.] Gupta, M. (2021). Impact of Influencer Marketing on Consumer Purchase Behavior during the Pandemic. International Journal of Innovative Research in Engineering & Multidisciplinary Physical Sciences. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Impact-of-Influencer-Marketing-on-Consumer-Purchase-Gupta/07aa126d14f8b1f4f3024c538e9d4f6ac6d74bfe>
- [20.] Hearn, Schoenhoff, (2015.) From Celebrity to Influencers https://books.google.com.qa/books?hl=en&lr=&id=mPTzBgAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PA194&dq=influencer+persona&ots=U_uN7vgElr&sig=aCdZB8Tg-9zECvUWg4YjbSe6VQo&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=influencer%20persona&f=false
- [21.] Hermanda, A., Sumarwan, U., & Tinaprillia, N. (2019). THE EFFECT OF SOCIAL MEDIA INFLUENCER ON BRAND IMAGE, SELF-CONCEPT, AND PURCHASE INTENTION. Journal of Consumer Sciences. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/THE-EFFECT-OF-SOCIAL-MEDIA-INFLUENCER-ON-BRAND-AND-Hermanda-Sumarwan/3ac405569a2a6b90d8590e7aa32038bafdc2b059>
- [22.] Home. (2019, August 14). Philippines School Doha. <https://psd.sch.qa/>
- [23.] Hyder, S. (2017, July 14). 3 ways to transform online connections into meaningful professional relationships. Inc.com. Retrieved December 1, 2021, from <https://www.inc.com/shama-hyder/three-ways-to-transform-online-connections-into-me.html>
- [24.] Ilianna Kwaske and Kay McLennan. (n.d.). Why Social Interaction is important in Online Learning. Retrieved September 21, 2021, from <https://sopa.tulane.edu/blog/why-social-interaction-important-online-learning>
- [25.] Jansen, Salminen, (2021). The What, Why, and How of Influencers and Personas! <https://persona.qcri.org/blog/the-what-why-and-how-of-influencers-and-personas/>
- [26.] Joei Chan (2019). We Analyzed 2.1M posts about Health and Wellness on Social Media. Here's What We Found... <https://www.linkfluence.com/blog/health-and-wellness-social-media/>
- [27.] Khamis, (2016). Self-branding, 'micro-celebrity' and the rise of Social Media Influencers <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/19392397.2016.1218292>
- [28.] Kostygina, G., Tran, H., Binns, S., Szczycka, G., Emery, S., Vallone, D., & Hair, E. (2020). Boosting Health Campaign Reach and Engagement Through Use of Social Media Influencers and Memes. Social Media + Society. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2056305120912475>
- [29.] Kumar A. and Priyadarshini (2018). Study to measure the impact of social media usage on work-life balance <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1757-899X/390/1/012045/meta>
- [30.] Kyte, (2021). The pressures - and rewards - of being an influencer <https://www.bbc.com/news/business-58487905>
- [31.] Lim, X.J., Radzol, A.R., Cheah, J., & Wong, M.W. (2017). The Impact of Social Media Influencers on Purchase Intention and the Mediation Effect of Customer Attitude. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/The-Impact-of-Social-Media-Influencers-on-Purchase-Lim-Radzol/0b4942142205ec1dc40e4d8f3e3d7f9a57748c09>
- [32.] Luca, M. (2016, August 5). User-generated content and social media. Handbook of Media Economics. Retrieved October 30, 2021, from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/B9780444636850000127>
- [33.] Lutkenhaus, Jansz, & Bouman (2019). Tailoring in the digital era: Stimulating dialogues on health topics in collaboration with social media influencers <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/2055207618821521>
- [34.] McCosker, A. (2018). Engaging mental health online: Insights from beyondblue's forum influencers. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444818784303>
- [35.] Media, M. D. S. (2019, July 9). 5 tips for content sharing across social platforms. Volume Nine. Retrieved December 1, 2021, from <https://www.v9digital.com/insights/content-sharing/>
- [36.] Nadja Enke & Nils Borchers (2019). Social media influencers in strategic communication: A conceptual framework for strategic social media influencer communication
- [37.] Newberry, (2021). Influencer Marketing Guide: How to Work With Social Media Influencers <https://blog.hootsuite.com/influencer-marketing/>
- [38.] Nils Borchers and Nadja Enke (2019). Managing strategic influencer communication: A systematic overview on emerging planning, organization, and controlling routines
- [39.] Noonan, M. (2018, November 3). Social Media Fitness Influencers: Innovators and Motivators. Iro.uiowa.edu. Retrieved October 23, 2021, from <https://iro.uiowa.edu/esploro/outputs/undergraduate/Soc>

- ial-Media-Fitness-Influencers-Innovators-and/9984111976102771?institution=01IOWA_INST
- [40.] Ouellette, D. (2012, July 30). The difficulty of influencing teams. *Fast Company*. Retrieved December 1, 2021, from <https://www.fastcompany.com/1512377/difficulty-influencing-teams>. Chan, J. (2019). We Analyzed 2.1M posts about Health and Wellness on Social Media. Here's What We Found...<https://www.linkfluence.com/blog/health-and-wellness-social-media>
- [41.] Partner, C. B., & Partner, L. R. (2020, January 17). Tackling your toughest influence challenges: Leading and ... Tackling Your Toughest Influence Challenges: Leading and Influencing in a Matrix. Retrieved September 21, 2021, from <https://info.vantagepartners.com/insights/tackling-your-toughest-influence-challenges-leading-and-influencing-in-a-matrix>
- [42.] Patel, (2021). What are Influencers: Types, Examples & How Much They Make<https://neilpatel.com/blog/guide-to-influencer-targeting/>
- [43.] Pendry, L. F., & Salvatore, J. (2015, April 20). Individual and social benefits of online discussion forums. *Computers in Human Behavior*. Retrieved October 23, 2021, from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S074756321500268X>
- [44.] Peng, J., Agarwal, A., Hosanagar, K., & Iyengar, R. (2018, August 1). Network overlap and content sharing on social media platforms - Jing Peng, Ashish Agarwal, Kartik Hosanagar, Raghuram Iyengar, 2018. *SAGE Journals*. Retrieved December 1, 2021, from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1509/jmr.14.0643> Lim, X.J., Radzol, A.R., Cheah, J., & Wong, M.W. (2017). The Impact of Social Media Influencers on Purchase Intention and the Mediation Effect of Customer Attitude. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/The-Impact-of-Social-Media-Influencers-on-Purchase-Lim-Radzol/0b4942142205ec1dc40e4d8f3e3d7f9a57748c09>
- [45.] Percherskyi, (2021) What is a Social Media Influencer?<https://promorepublic.com/en/blog/glossary/what-is-social-media-influencer/>
- [46.] Robinson L. and Smith M. (2020, September). Social Media and Mental Health: <https://www.helpguide.org/articles/mental-health/social-media-and-mental-health.htm#:~:text=The%20negative%20aspects%20of%20social%20media&text=However%2C%20multiple%20studies%20have%20found,about%20your%20life%20or%20appearance.>
- [47.] Shane Barker. (2019, August 20). 5 Challenges Most Micro-Influencers Deal With. Retrieved September 21, 2021, from <https://thenextscoop.com/challenges-micro-influencers-deal-with/>
- [48.] Sukovic, S. (n.d.). Explore scientific, technical, and medical research on ScienceDirect. ScienceDirect.com | Science, health and medical journals, full text articles and books. Retrieved October 30, 2021, from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/>
- [49.] Team, F. (2021, February 10). The psychology of content sharing online in 2021 [research]. *Foundation Marketing*. Retrieved December 1, 2021, from <https://foundationinc.co/lab/psychology-sharing-content-online/>
- [50.] Troncoso, (2021) 10 Best Persona Examples And How To Create Your Own<https://marketsplash.com/persona-examples/>
- [51.] Valdez L, (2019) Influencer Ambitions? Top 5 Tips For Success<https://www.ovostudio.co.uk/2019/12/13/influencer-amitions/>
- [52.] Vanderkam, L. (2014, June 17). How to transform online connections into real-life relationships. *Fast Company*. Retrieved December 1, 2021, from <https://www.fastcompany.com/3031969/how-to-transform-online-connections-into-real-life-relationships>
- [53.] Wang, Anping, (2020) Influencer persona and audience engagement : an analysis of the user decision-making differences between traditional and short-video-based social media. <https://dspace.mit.edu/handle/1721.1/132836>
- [54.] Wellman L, (2020). What it means to be a bodybuilder: social media influencer labor and the construction of identity in the bodybuilding subculture<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/10714421.2020.1829303>
- [55.] Yılmaz, M., Uzuner, Y., & Sezerel, H. (2020, May 13). Why Social Interaction is important in Online Learning. Sharing experiences and interpretation of experiences: a phenomenological research on Instagram influencers. Retrieved September 21, 2021, from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13683500.2020.1763270>
- [56.] Zak, S., & Hasprova, M. (2020). The role of influencers in the consumer decision-making process. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/pape/The-role-of-influencers-in-the-consumer-process-Zak-Hasprova/2d0cbda77a659302271fa48f4173a4fb12993c31>

WORDS OF GRATITUDE

We would like to express our sincerest gratitude and appreciation to our Research Adviser, **Mr. Efren L. Burgos** for his continuous efforts to help and guide us during the writing of our Research. He is our 11th Grade class adviser who dedicates his time to motivate his students in doing their best and to do good deeds in any way possible. His knowledge, patience and timely

assistance have made it possible for us to finish our paper. We thank you so much for the proper guidance and support you have given to our research team. You are undoubtedly one of the main motivators to accomplishing this research paper and we will remain grateful for having you as our Research Adviser.

We also thank **Dr. Fredelito Don John A. Vallesteros and Mr. Danilo N. Keh, Jr.** for being our Research Teachers during our 11th Grade. Their lectures about IMRaD Research Paper have been a big help in building our foundation in our research paper. Their dedication in teaching in the field of Research has helped mold us to the researchers we are up to this present. A big thanks to their trust in this paper.

We would also like to thank our **family and friends** for their constant love and support. They have always been an inspiration for us to continue working hard and to aim for higher learning.

We are especially grateful to our **Almighty God** for continuously showering us with his blessings and wisdom.

GLOSSARY OF TERMS

The following terms were defined conceptually and operationally to add ease of understanding.

- **Cool** –It is the analyzation of data, which is the first step after arriving the final transcription
- **Warm**- It is the final data that leads to identifying the emergent themes
- **Dendrogram**- a branching diagram representing a hierarchy of categories based on degree of similarity or number of shared characteristics (Merriam-Webster. (n.d.). Dendrogram. In Merriam-Webster.com dictionary.
- **Emic**- responses that were sent originally by the participants
- **Etic**- It is the transcribed responses from the respondents by the researchers
- **Phenomenology**- the study of the development of human consciousness and self-awareness as a preface to or a part of philosophy (Merriam-Webster. (n.d.). Phenomenology. In *Merriam-Webster.com dictionary*.
- **Philippine School Doha**- It is a learning institute in Qatar established in 1992, used as the local of the study.
- **Robofoto**- which is prepared to get the respondents' demographic profile given by each student. Thereafter, the nature of the study, the meaning of each attribute and level were discussed. (Braganza, De Guzman, Gonzaga, and Llamasares (2016). *A Conjoint Analysis of the Listening Activity Preferences of a Select Group of Grade 7 and 8 Students from Philippine Provincial Schools, Vol. 4 No. 7 July 2016, (473)*.
- **Influencer Personas'**- personas for an influencer essentially are pictorial representations of the characteristics of an influencer's audience. These influencer audience personas can help influencers in crafting their social media posts and have more focused messages for their audience. (Persona Writer (February 7, 2021) *The What, Why, and How of Influencers and Personas!*. In *persona.qcri.org blog*.
- **Platform Distinctiveness**- The influencer's associated social media platform, talks about the individuality of an influencer and how an influencer separates him/herself from others.
- **Ambition Orientedness**- It's the influencer's mindset pursuing his/her goal. Under this subtheme, the potential influencers seek how to become social media influencers, it talks about the different encouragement and inspirations that allows the influencer to continue his/her career. While enjoying their career and their passion for social media influencing, they inspire others while inspiring themselves. That is how they motivate themselves.
- **Detail Meticulousness**- This sub theme talks about the influencers thought process when posting content, the influencer considers the standards that were formulated from the influencer and the audience.
- **Online Interaction**- Online interaction is that in marketing, consumers communicate or interact with each other, with the business or with the brand, and this is done in an online environment. (PinarYürük-Kayapınar (2021) *Examination of Empirical Studies on Customer Engagement, Online Engagement, and Social Media Engagement*.
- **Online Connections**- usually refers to an Internet connection, but in terms of people, it refers to the relationship of people throughout the online platforms they use.
- **Content Sharing**- refers to the strategic distribution webpage and blog content across relevant social media such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Google +.

- **Influencing Difficulties**- The hardships, problems or obstacles that get in the way of having an effect or having an influence on.
- **Holistic Health**- is an approach to life that considers multidimensional aspects of wellness. It encourages individuals to recognize the whole person: physical, mental, emotional, social, intellectual, and spiritual.
- **Healthy Living** - an even distribution of schedules on a daily basis.
- **Balancing Routine** - is having the opportunity and ability to act in a certain way that affects your physical and mental well – being, positively.
- **Strengthening Relationships** - adept at valuing other people and showing concern for others.

BIOGRAPHICAL DATA

Gwyneth Ghaile S. Von Giese is currently in the 12th grade in senior high under the GAS (General Academics Strand) of Philippine School Doha, Qatar. Born on November 6, 2003. She participated in Intramurals during her Junior years; badminton which she received a Silver Award for 2 consecutive years (2013-2014) and a Bronze Award in Table Tennis 2018. She was also President of her class from Grade 4-5, Grade 7-10, and Vice President Grade 11-12. She directed and scripted a play for her class during the Academic Olympiad in 2015 that won the champion. She graduated her intermediate year with an award of GSP. Besides that, she is constantly in the Top 10 in her class. In her 10th Grade, she became part of the C.A.T Group and graduated JHS with an award of Cadette of the Year. Now in her senior years, she has attended multiple and various seminars regarding research. She was top 1 thrice in her 11th year and was a Laureola Awardee for both semesters. She also received most of the “Best in” in their subjects. After she graduates from Senior High School in April 2022, she will be pursuing her career to be a nurse at the University of Calgary.

Byron Vince Blanco is currently in the 12th grade in senior high under the GAS (General Academics Strand) of Philippine School Doha, Qatar. Born on December 25, 2002. In his Junior High school, he was part of the Top 10 in their class, and in his Senior High school, he was also part of the Top 10 during the second semester. In his 10th Grade, he received Mythical Five in Intramurals. After graduating in April 2022, he will pursue his chosen career which is to be a Business Entrepreneur in De La Salle University.

Mark Kevin M. Chavez is currently in the 12th Grade in the Senior high School under the GAS (General Academic Strand) of Philippine School Doha, Qatar. He took part during the 2019 Intramurals for volleyball boys to which he and his team won as the first runner up and on the same year he and his group from 10-Edison won as the champions for the Manipulative Toy Making Contest during the Science Fair. Also, on the same year, he received a certificate of recognition for the Best Computer System Servicing with a grade 90 and another certificate of recognition for Best Computer System Servicing with a grade of 97. After he graduates in April 2022, he will be pursuing his career which is becoming a Computer Engineer at Mapua Institute of Technology.

Justin Arnel P. Cornejo, a Grade 12 Student who is taking GAS as a strand in Philippine School Doha, got the highest grading in 11th in the subject “reading and writing”. He has his love for music, that he joined a band back in Grade 10 for his section. Used to get perfect attendance through his school years. before, he wasn’t that great in studies but now he is hoping to change that part of himself for the better, to improve himself and to be more independent. Throughout the time being in the GAS strand, he now knows who and what he wanted to be, and his aim is to be a psychologist in the future. After he will graduate from PSD, he plans to pursue being a professional psychologist in Canada. With the motto “to live your life to the fullest in the

present”

Racel Gwen S. Encarnacion is currently a Senior high school as GAS student in Philippine School Doha. She had won several awards at school. She participated in HMCI's Interpretation Dance and won first place. She was also a former student council un HMCI and given the opportunity to be a C.A.T commandant flight Alpha. In 2020 she received an award of most improved student among the class. After she graduates in Senior high school on April 2022, she plans to continue studying and pursue Nursing in the Far Eastern University. Believes in the motto that “When you know better, do better.”

Alliah TJ S. Hipolito is currently in Senior High School as a GAS (General Academic Strand) student in Philippine School Doha. With the reputation of being the Top 14 in the 1st semester of her grade 12 year. She has been a Laureolla Qualifier in grade 11, (2nd semester) as well as being in the consistent top in the class. Adding to her credit in research, her research group was chosen as best research in grade 10 and got to showcase it to her fellow schoolmates. During the intramurals in grade 10 and 9, she was part of being the overall champion and not to mention her zero demerit during CAT on grade 10. Even during her early days in Philippine School Doha, she was the “Miss photogenic” for United Nations (Ms. China) an on-and-off pilot class student and bronze awardee during preparatory. She dreams of pursuing Respiratory therapist at the College of North Atlantic-Qatar (CNAQ). Afterwards, she will continue her studies to become an emergency medicine doctor.

Abdul-Raiz H. Ali Marabur Is a 12th GAS Student in the Philippine School Doha. He participated in the world’s first tournament, in 2015 He was given the opportunity to Join the bowling tournament and he plans to continue his at the National University located in Manila.

Abram Vinzell L. Pacia is currently in the 12th grade in senior high under the GAS (General Academics Strand) strand of Philippine School Doha, Qatar. He has participated over multiple seminars regarding research throughout his senior high. He became best in Science and Music during his younger years as an academic award along with getting a medal for becoming great in Singing which is an event inside the school, while being a first runner-up on his basketball team earning a silver medal, and being a champion on his basketball team the upcoming year earning him a gold medal as an award for outside school events, on his 10th grade as a student in the junior high department, he became best in Computer Systems Servicing, and during his 11th grade, being a student of the senior high department for the first time, he gained an achievement becoming top 2 of his class. After he will be graduating from high school on April 2022, he will be pursuing his career choice which is becoming a Cardiothoracic Surgeon in Fatima University in Valenzuela, Philippines.

Liam John Roque is a current grade 12 GAS student in Philippines School Doha. In his stay in PSD he has been an active student since kindergarten and has achieved multiple achievements from participating in events. He has been a part of multiple performances, extracurricular activities, sports events and achieved class ranks and recognition. He was part of the basketball team Underdawgz that won the 2019-2020 PTA basketball student category championship. After graduating from PSD he plans to pursue a bachelor's degree in accounting at the College of North Atlantic - Qatar.

Gem Danielle V. Tuquib is currently in the 12th grade enrolled in Philippine School Doha, Qatar as a GAS student. Over the years she has achieved a few class ranks, subject and performance recognitions, and extracurricular awards. Apart from these she also participated in club organizations, subject programs, and sports events. After graduating her last year in K-12, she will be pursuing her goal as a Nurse at Cebu Doctors University, and continue her education and career abroad. Believing in the motto “when nothing goes right, go left”.